

HEALTH PROBLEMS AND VITAMIN C IN CANADIAN NORTHERN MILITARY OPERATIONS

DCIEM REPORT NO. 74-R-1012

MARCH 1974

B.H. SABISTON
M.W. RADOMSKI

The RCT by Sabiston and Radomski (1974) is made available with the permission of the editor of DRDC Toronto, see the last page of this document.

In 2009, Harri Hemilä asked Dr. Manny Radomski for certain methodological details about the trial and his answers are on the following pages.

This RCT has been cited in:

Hemilä H. Vitamin C and common cold incidence: a review of studies with subjects under heavy physical stress. *Int J Sports Med.* 1996;17(5):379-83.

<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2007-972864>

<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10250/7983>

which reported a meta-analysis of 3 RCTs with physically stressed participants and found on average a 50% decrease in the risk of colds: RR = 0.50; 95% CI 0.35, 0.69.

Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold.

Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013;2013(1):CD000980.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub4>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc8078152>

<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/225864>

which updated the above meta-analysis with physically stressed participants, including 2 further 2 RCTs (i.e. a total of 5 RCTs with participants under heavy acute physical stress) and found that the halving of the risk of colds remained but the confidence interval became slightly smaller: RR = 0.48; 95% CI 0.35, 0.64.

Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and respiratory infections: a systematic review.

Mil Med. 2004;169(11):920-5.

<https://doi.org/10.7205/milmed.169.11.920>

<https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/225867>

which reviewed vitamin C and respiratory infection trials with military personnel and with other subjects living under crowded conditions comparable to those of military recruits, and demonstrated strong evidence that vitamin C has effects in such conditions.

The report is in two versions below, the first is with optical character recognition of the text, and the second with an ordinary unaltered scan of the text.

Harri Hemila

From: "Manny Radomski" <mwradoski@sympatico.ca>
To: "Harri Hemila" <harri.hemila@helsinki.fi>
Sent: 12. syyskuuta 2009 22:05
Subject: Re: Vitamin C report

Dear Dr. Hemila,

Thank you for all of the information that you sent reference your work on Vitamin C. We have examined your questions reference our study and have the following comments to add:

1. Well, we should probably kick ourselves, but the reason we did not publish in the scientific literature is that we wanted to replicate our data in another arctic trial under exactly the same conditions and trial design parameters. Unfortunately, we never had an opportunity to participate in another military exercise to be able to replicate our trial. Time went by and we thought that our trial data was 'old news'. Unfortunately our data did not elicit much interest from the military medical branch, and it is difficult to tag onto a military trial and obtain their full cooperation. We were fortunate in that we received full cooperation from the field commanders.
2. Yes, we did assign people randomly. We had the names of people beforehand but we assigned them randomly and we provided their names on the pill vials. The Tent Group Commander was responsible for distributing the pills and recording the distribution. He did NOT know what was in the vials.
3. Yes, it was Double-Blind. While we pre-assigned Vit C and Placebo randomly, we did not break the code until after the trial. Two labelled vials were provided to the Tent Group Commanders but the Tent Group Commanders did NOT know what was in the vials. They just knew who to give the pills to. We did not label the vials Vit C and Placebo but, as I recall, we assigned a Number to the Vials which was coded to Vit C or Placebo.
6. The Vit C and Placebo were in identical capsules, so taste did not enter into the equation. We obtained the empty Placebo capsules from the Vit C supplier and then we filled the Placebo capsules in the lab. Pretty sure we used Sucrose.
4. In our pre-briefing to the troops, we believe that we told the troops that they would all be getting Vitamin C but at different doses.
5. We collected the data by symptoms on T-Scan cards. We then came up with a 'scoring' system to define a cold, totally independent of examining any data. Then, three of us sat down and assigned 'scores' to each card without any knowledge, at all, with respect to Vit C or Placebo. We re-visited several cards, several times, to arrive at a consensus opinion. We did not 'break the code' until after all cards had been assessed.

The environment in which we carried out the trial of Vitamin C was quite unique - first because of external conditions and the daily workload and stress imposed upon the soldiers. Secondly, they were housed in a very

confining environment (10 men to a tent) in very close proximity to each other which was optimal for any transfer of infection. This made our findings even more significant as vitamin C passed under very severe conditions. Linus Pauling in his book published after our study took our data and reanalyzed it and came away with a stronger conclusion than we did as to the benefits of vitamin C in moderating and alleviating the severity of cold symptoms.

In your "risk of bias table", we can say say to the four factors listed in your table.

We would be pleased to provide any further clarification, our memories permitting!!!

Kindest regards,

Manny Radomski

----- Original Message -----

From: "Harri Hemila" <harri.hemila@helsinki.fi>
 To: "Manny Radomski" <mwradomski@sympatico.ca>
 Sent: Wednesday, September 02, 2009 12:14 PM
 Subject: Re: Vitamin C report

> Dear Prof. Radomski,
 >
 > Thank you very much for contacting me.
 > Please, see the attachments.
 > Print the "Radomski_" file and there you will see my question.
 >
 > Yours sincerely,
 >
 > Harri
 >
 > Harri Hemilä, PhD, MD
 > Docent (associate professor)
 > Department of Public Health, POB 41
 > University of Helsinki
 > Helsinki, FIN-00014
 > Finland
 >
 >
 >
 >
 > Manny Radomski wrote:
 >> Dear Harri,
 >>
 >> Your email was passed to me. I am surprised that you were able to dig
 >> up a reference to our Vitamin C paper. I would be pleased to answer
 >> any questions that you might have reference our report.
 >>
 >> Regards,
 >>
 >> Manny Radomski

>> Professor Emeritus

>>

>>

>

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HEALTH PROBLEMS AND VITAMIN C IN CANADIAN NORTHERN MILITARY OPERATIONS

**B.H. SABISTON
M.W. RADOMSKI**

(Text of Communication presented at the Twenty-Fifth Symposium of the Defence Research Board, Department of National Defence, Canada. Presented 14 November 1973 by B.H. Sabiston)

Biosciences Division

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DEFENCE RESEARCH BOARD — DEPARTMENT OF NATIONAL DEFENCE — CANADA

ABSTRACT

As part of a continuing study of health problems pertinent to Canadian Northern Military operations, two aspects of Vitamin C have been examined in land element personnel participating on Northern Winter Exercises. This report describes results of an ongoing Vitamin C survey designed to examine both the Vitamin C status of troops and the effects of a daily Vitamin C supplement on the incidence and severity of colds in troops undergoing operational training. Results indicate that a daily 1000 mg supplement of Vitamin C reduced significantly the incidence of colds as assessed on the basis of symptom complexes reported on health survey cards. While the overall incidence of colds was influenced significantly by Vitamin C, both on an individual and a tent group basis, the duration of local cold symptoms was not. In those individuals who contracted a cold, nasal and throat and chest symptoms were observed to persist for similar periods of time in both placebo and Vitamin C supplemented groups. The Vitamin C group, however, did show a significant reduction in the duration of the more constitutional symptoms related to a general feeling of "well-being". The Vitamin C status of individuals was assessed on the basis of whole blood ascorbate levels determined before and after participation on Northern exercises. A significant reduction of whole blood ascorbate was observed post-exercise on three separate serials of Exercise New Viking, the troops of which were supplied with RP-4 field rations. In view of the fact that only a minor reduction of whole blood ascorbate was observed on another serial, the troops of which were supplied with IRP field rations, it is not possible to determine whether the reduction in ascorbate status was a reflection of altered dietary intake or an increased requirement for Vitamin C under the activity and exposure conditions experienced on Northern operations. Further work is required to clarify this situation.

HEALTH PROBLEMS AND VITAMIN C IN CANADIAN NORTHERN MILITARY OPERATIONS

Since the early part of 1972, the Biosciences Division of the Defence and Civil Institute of Environmental Medicine (DCIEM) has been involved in an extensive field program designed to examine some of the health problems pertinent to Canadian Northern Military operations.

Table 1 lists some of the potential health problem areas encountered in a transit military population operating under Arctic or sub-Arctic conditions. These have been divided, somewhat arbitrarily, into two groups: Environmental and Operational.

TABLE 1
POTENTIAL HEALTH PROBLEM AREAS
NORTHERN OPERATIONS

ENVIRONMENTAL	OPERATIONAL
Cold Injury	Nutrition
Frostbite	Rations
Trench Foot	Dehydration
Hypothermia	Constipation
Snow Blindness	Tent Eye
Sunburn	Physical Fitness
Cold Sores	Wound Healing
	Upper Respiratory
	Infection
	Dental

(1) *Environmental* problems are those which arise as a consequence of *direct insult upon the individual by his environment.*

(2) *Operational* problems are those which arise as a consequence of *restrictions placed upon an individual by his environment.*

This report describes results dealing with some problems in the operational category, specifically with regard to rations and Vitamin C, the Vitamin C status of individuals, and the effect of Vitamin C supplementation on symptoms of respiratory distress.

One of the approaches which has been applied throughout the field program has been the administration of a health survey to men taking part in military winter exercises. This survey was established primarily to answer the questions, "does the abrupt introduction of a man into the Northern climate produce any demonstrable change in health pattern? If so, what is the nature of this alteration? "

The majority of health surveys which have investigated environmental factors impinging on health have been concerned with indigenous populations or isolated communities. Data derived from such studies are not applicable directly to transit populations such as members of mobile military forces. Recognition of this fact prompted DCIEM to establish a protocol for obtaining epidemiologic data on military men making periodic excursions into the North. The survey has been restricted to members of the land element for it is these individuals who are exposed most directly to the adverse environment for periods of greater than a few hours.

Table 2 lists the exercises which have been surveyed to date. With one exception (Northern Ramble, May 1972) the field program has utilized men taking part in New Viking training exercises. It is important to recognize the fact that these are *training* exercises and that as such, the men are living under the most "ideal" Arctic conditions in the sense that experienced instructors are with them at all times. Consequently, the men are under constant supervision to ensure that they protect themselves adequately from the environment. Hence, any health problems which arise on such exercises should be taken as a minimal estimate of problems which may arise on more operational missions.

TABLE 2
NORTHERN EXERCISES UTILIZED FOR THE
INVESTIGATION OF HEALTH PROBLEMS, 1972-73

Exercise	Date	Home CFB	N	Northern Location
New Viking 37	March 1972	Petawawa	70	Coral Harbor
Northern Ramble	May 1972	London	400	Churchill
New Viking 49	December 1972	London	100	Coral Harbor
New Viking 52	January 1973	Gagetown	100	Churchill
New Viking 55	February 1973	Petawawa	100	Frobisher Bay
New Viking 56	March 1973	Calgary	120	Frobisher Bay
New Viking 57	April 1973	Petawawa	100	Frobisher Bay

The health survey card used in the collection of field data is shown in Figure 1. The health survey has been conducted on an individual tent-group basis and extensive use has been made of the tent-group commanders who have been responsible for administering the survey cards on a daily basis. The survey period has extended typically from one week before the exercise to one week after the exercise. Tabulation of the incidence of individual symptoms and symptom complexes has been carried out post-exercise and it has become apparent that, to one degree or another, the incidence of individual symptoms is affected by movement into the North. The most marked alteration in symptoms reported has been noted in symptoms related to the upper respiratory system and it is these symptoms which have been examined in greater detail in DCIEM Vitamin C studies.

An assessment of Vitamin C was undertaken for a number of reasons:

(1) The whole question of Vitamin C and its effect on colds is a topical and debatable issue. It was hoped that some light would be shed on this problem by utilizing a very restricted population of comparable age, typical cold history, common dietary regimen, activity schedule and environmental exposure.

(2) It has been suggested that Vitamin C may play a role in increasing cold tolerance - with particular regard to maintaining peripheral circulation.

(3) Finally, it was determined that the RP-4 rations (1970-71) on which the men were living, apparently provided a maximum of 37-41 mg Vitamin C per day in a single fruit-drink mix. As previous observations suggested that the fruit-drink mix was an unpopular item in the rations and tended to be discarded, it appeared that the individual intake of Vitamin C could be below the recommended daily allowance.

Accordingly, a protocol was established for dispensing tablets of either Vitamin C or placebo to individuals in each tent. Men in each tent group were assigned randomly to either the Vitamin C or placebo group. Extensive use was made again, of tent-group commanders who carried with them the supply of pills for their own tent. Two pill vials were provided for each tent, one containing Vitamin C and one containing placebo. Each vial contained the names of the men who were to receive the respective pills. Pills were dispensed twice a day, once with the morning meal and once with the evening meal. The total dose of Vitamin C received each day was 1000 mg.

At the completion of the exercise the incidence and duration of colds was examined by assessing the presence or absence of a cold on the basis of symptom constellations. In order for a man to be classified as having a cold, he had to have two nasal symptoms in conjunction with a minimum of sore throat or chest cough which persisted for two or more days. As a further restriction, the sore throat or chest cough had to be absent at the time the nasal symptoms began. Frequently, it was found that more constitutional symptoms such as headache, chills and fever, general malaise, nausea or vomiting were indicated at some time during the symptom constellation.

Table 3 indicates that the random allocation of men to the two treatment groups resulted in two well-matched populations with respect to age and typical cold history.

TABLE 3
THE MEAN AGE AND COMMON COLD HISTORY OF MEMBERS OF A
SINGLE INFANTRY COMPANY OF 112 MEN ALLOCATED
RANDOMLY TO VITAMIN C AND PLACEBO PREPARATIONS

Group	N	Age	Incidence of Usual Spring Cold %
Vitamin C	56	25.3 ± 6.3* (Range 17 - 40)	61.6
Placebo	56	25.4 ± 8.1 (Range 17 - 47)	60.0

*Mean ± S.D.

Table 4 depicts the frequency of colds assessed in a single infantry company on a Northern Military exercise. The incidence of colds in two other companies participating on the exercise, but not subjected to pill supplementation, was 21.0% and 29.4% respectively.

TABLE 4
INDIVIDUAL INCIDENCE OF COLDS ASSESSED IN A
SINGLE INFANTRY COMPANY OF 112 MEN PARTICIPATING
ON A NORTHERN MILITARY EXERCISE

Group	N	Frequency	Percent Frequency
Vitamin C	56	6	10.7
Placebo	56	14	25.0
χ^2	3.87		P=0.05

The results indicate that the Vitamin C group experienced significantly fewer colds than the corresponding placebo group. This ameliorating effect of Vitamin C was also reflected in the frequency of colds reported by individual tent groups (Table 5). Of the 14 tent groups involved in this study, nine groups (64.3%) indicated the presence of at least one cold during the exercise period. Of these nine groups, six (66.6%) indicated colds present only in placebo individuals, whereas the remaining three (33.3%) indicated colds present in both placebo and Vitamin C groups. In no case did a tent group indicate the presence of colds in Vitamin C individuals only.

TABLE 5
TENT GROUP INCIDENCE OF COLDS IN AN INFANTRY
COMPANY OF 112 MEN PARTICIPATING ON A NORTHERN MILITARY EXERCISE

Number of Tent Groups Reporting One or More Colds Amongst its Members	Number of Tent Groups Indicating Colds Present		
	In Vitamin C Individuals only	In Placebo Individuals only	In Both Vitamin C and Placebo Individuals
9/14	0/9	6/9	3/9
(64.3%)	—	(66.6%)	(33.3%)

The data presented in Table 6 indicate that despite a reduction in the frequency of colds in Vitamin C individuals, the duration of cold symptoms as related to the presence of nasal, throat or chest complaints was not significantly influenced. In other words, if an individual experienced a cold while on Vitamin C, the continued daily intake of 1000 mg/day did not alter the course of the cold with respect to the local symptoms. Examination of the more constitutional symptoms however (Table 7) revealed that the duration of these was significantly reduced in the Vitamin C group. This perhaps is a significant finding for it is these symptoms which are related to the general feeling of "well-being" and it is these symptoms which, in a civilian population, could predispose a person to remain at home. In a military population where refuge cannot be sought easily, it is these symptoms which would tend to reduce a man's level of effectiveness.

TABLE 6
THE MEAN DURATION OF UPPER RESPIRATORY SYMPTOMS
REPORTED BY MEN AFFLICTED WITH A COMMON COLD

Group	N	Duration of Symptoms (days)	
		Nasal	Throat/Chest
Vitamin C	6	4.2 ± 3.8*	4.3 ± 3.0
Placebo	14	5.6 ± 2.8	6.0 ± 3.0
P		> 0.4 > 0.5	> 0.2 > 0.3

*Mean ± S.D.

TABLE 7
THE MEAN DURATION OF CONSTITUTIONAL SYMPTOMS
RELATED TO A FEELING OF WELL-BEING REPORTED
BY MEN AFFLICTED WITH A COMMON COLD

Group	N	Duration of Symptoms (days)
Vitamin C	6	0.8 ± 0.8*
Placebo	14	2.4 ± 2.1
		p < 0.05

On subsequent exercises an examination of the Vitamin C status of men was carried out by examining the whole-blood ascorbate levels before and immediately after the exercise. Table 8 shows the incidence of altered ascorbate status on four Northern exercises. In all cases, a significant number of men demonstrated a decrease in whole-blood ascorbate, however the magnitude of this decrease (Table 9) was significant on only three of the exercises. Coincidentally, these three exercises were supplied with the RP4 ration while the fourth exercise (Serial 56) received IRP field rations. The IRP ration provides approximately 50–90 mg of Vitamin C per day, about 50% of which is in a single fruit-drink mix and 50% is distributed throughout other ration components.

TABLE 8
INCIDENCE OF ALTERED WHOLE-BLOOD ASCORBATE STATUS
OCCURRING ON NORTHERN EXERCISES

Serial	N	% of Individuals Demonstrating a Decrease in Ascorbate	% of Individuals below 0.50 mg% Ascorbate	
			Pre-Exercise	Post-Exercise
NV 49	86	70	4	8
NV 51	29	83	28	41
NV 55	24	46	21	12
NV 56	34	47	32	32

TABLE 9
MEAN WHOLE-BLOOD ASCORBATE STATUS BEFORE AND
AFTER PARTICIPATION ON NORTHERN EXERCISES

Serial	N	Pre-Exercise Level mg%	Post-Exercise Mean Change	
			mg%	%
NV 49	86	1.05 ± 0.04*	-0.19 ± 0.04	-18
NV 51	29	0.86 ± 0.07	-0.21 ± 0.04	-24
NV 55	24	0.91 ± 0.10	-0.13 ± 0.06	-14
NV 56	34	0.76 ± 0.05	-0.03 ± 0.06	- 4

*Mean ± S.E.M.

One further point with reference to Table 8 is the rather surprising number of men who demonstrated whole-blood ascorbate levels lower than 0.50 mg%. This value is generally taken to indicate the threshold of a possible sub-clinical scorbutic condition. Two of the four serials examined post-exercise demonstrated a definite shift towards this subclinical scorbutic state, one (Serial 56) remained unchanged and the other (Serial 55) demonstrated a shift in the opposite direction.

In view of the variation in diet and distribution of change in ascorbate status, it is not possible from these data to determine whether the reduction in ascorbate levels, observed post-exercise on three of the four serials, was a consequence of reduced dietary intake of Vitamin C or a reflection of a possible increased requirement for this vitamin under the activity and exposure conditions existing on Northern operations. Clearly, a determination of ascorbate excretion is required before any estimate of requirement under these conditions can be made.

This study is part of a continuing program to assess the nature and incidence of health problems pertinent to Canadian military Northern operations. With regards to Vitamin C and its influence on general body health the data to date suggest that a daily supplement of 1000 mg Vitamin C appears to reduce the overall incidence of colds in transit military populations. It must be appreciated however, that the nature of the military exercise itself represents a marked departure from the "normal" daily routine. Over the period of this study, the men are transported by air into an adverse environment and live in close association with that

environment. Their dietary regimen is altered dramatically with regards both to frequency of meals and nature of food eaten. In view of these factors the results reported here do not necessarily characterize the civilian population in general. Further, insufficient data exist to enable us to determine whether the observed beneficial effect of Vitamin C observed in this study, is prophylactic or therapeutic, although the analysis of colds by tent groups suggests that the effect may be prophylactic. In addition the study was restricted to an examination of the efficacy of a daily 1000 mg dose of Vitamin C, which may represent neither the optimal nor minimal daily supplement required. The whole-blood ascorbate levels of individuals receiving a Vitamin C supplement were increased well above normal (100–150%). In view of the demonstrated decrease in whole-blood ascorbate occurring in non-supplemented men, the optimal dose of Vitamin C may be in a range which is sufficient to prevent such a decrease. Further work is required to clarify this situation.

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NORTHERN OPERATIONS

ENVIRONMENTAL	OPERATIONAL
Cold Injury Frostbite Trench Foot Hypothermia Snow Blindness Sunburn Cold Sores	Nutrition Rations Dehydration Constipation Tent Eye Physical Fitness Wound Healing Upper Respiratory Infection Dental

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(2) It has been suggested that Vitamin C may play a role in increasing cold tolerance – with particular regard to maintaining peripheral circulation.

(3) Finally, it was determined that the RP-4 rations (1970-71) on which the men were living, apparently provided a maximum of 37-41 mg Vitamin C per day in a single fruit-drink mix. As previous observations suggested that the fruit-drink mix was an unpopular item in the rations and tended to be discarded, it appeared that the individual intake of Vitamin C could be below the recommended daily allowance.

Accordingly, a protocol was established for dispensing tablets of either Vitamin C or placebo to individuals in each tent. Men in each tent group were assigned randomly to either the Vitamin C or placebo group. Extensive use was made again, of tent-group commanders who carried with them the supply of pills for their own tent. Two pill vials were provided for each tent, one containing Vitamin C and one containing placebo. Each vial contained the names of the men who were to receive the respective pills. Pills were dispensed twice a day, once with the morning meal and once with the evening meal. The total dose of Vitamin C received each day was 1000 mg.

At the completion of the exercise the incidence and duration of colds was examined by assessing the presence or absence of a cold on the basis of symptom constellations. In order for a man to be classified as having a cold, he had to have two nasal symptoms in conjunction with a minimum of sore throat or chest cough which persisted for two or more days. As a further restriction, the sore throat or chest cough had to be absent at the time the nasal symptoms began. Frequently, it was found that more constitutional symptoms such as headache, chills and fever, general malaise, nausea or vomiting were indicated at some time during the symptom constellation.

Table 3 indicates that the random allocation of men to the two treatment groups resulted in two well-matched populations with respect to age and typical cold history.

TABLE 3
THE MEAN AGE AND COMMON COLD HISTORY OF MEMBERS OF
A SINGLE INFANTRY COMPANY OF 112 MEN ALLOCATED
RANDOMLY TO VITAMIN C AND PLACEBO PREPARATIONS

Group	N	Age	Incidence of Usual Spring Cold %
Vitamin C	56	25.3 ± 6.3* (Range 17 - 40)	61.6
Placebo	56	25.4 ± 8.1 (Range 17 - 47)	60.0

*Mean ± S.D.

Table 4 depicts the frequency of colds assessed in a single infantry company on a Northern Military exercise. The incidence of colds in two other companies participating on the exercise, but not subjected to pill supplementation, was 21.0% and 29.4% respectively.

TABLE 4
INDIVIDUAL INCIDENCE OF COLDS ASSESSED IN A
SINGLE INFANTRY COMPANY OF 112 MEN PARTICIPATING
ON A NORTHERN MILITARY EXERCISE

Group	N	Frequency	Percent Frequency
Vitamin C	56	6	10.7
Placebo	56	14	25.0
χ^2	3.87		P=0.05

The results indicate that the Vitamin C group experienced significantly fewer colds than the corresponding placebo group. This ameliorating effect of Vitamin C was also reflected in the frequency of colds reported by individual tent groups (Table 5). Of the 14 tent groups involved in this study, nine groups (64.3%) indicated the presence of at least one cold during the exercise period. Of these nine groups, six (66.6%) indicated colds present only in placebo individuals, whereas the remaining three (33.3%) indicated colds present in both placebo and Vitamin C groups. In no case did a tent group indicate the presence of colds in Vitamin C individuals only.

TABLE 5
TENT GROUP INCIDENCE OF COLDS IN AN INFANTRY
COMPANY OF 112 MEN PARTICIPATING ON A NORTHERN MILITARY EXERCISE

Number of Tent Groups Reporting One or More Colds Amongst its Members	Number of Tent Groups Indicating Colds Present		
	In Vitamin C Individuals only	In Placebo Individuals only	In Both Vitamin C and Placebo Individuals
9/14	0/9	6/9	3/9
(64.3%)	—	(66.6%)	(33.3%)

The data presented in Table 6 indicate that despite a reduction in the frequency of colds in Vitamin C individuals, the duration of cold symptoms as related to the presence of nasal, throat or chest complaints was not significantly influenced. In other words, if an individual experienced a cold while on Vitamin C, the continued daily intake of 1000 mg/day did not alter the course of the cold with respect to the local symptoms. Examination of the more constitutional symptoms however (Table 7) revealed that the duration of these was significantly reduced in the Vitamin C group. This perhaps is a significant finding for it is these symptoms which are related to the general feeling of "well-being" and it is these symptoms which, in a civilian population, could predispose a person to remain at home. In a military population where refuge cannot be sought easily, it is these symptoms which would tend to reduce a man's level of effectiveness.

TABLE 6
THE MEAN DURATION OF UPPER RESPIRATORY SYMPTOMS
REPORTED BY MEN AFFLICTED WITH A COMMON COLD

Group	N	Duration of Symptoms (days)	
		Nasal	Throat/Chest
Vitamin C	6	4.2 ± 3.8*	4.3 ± 3.0
Placebo	14	5.6 ± 2.8	6.0 ± 3.0
P		> 0.4 > 0.5	> 0.2 > 0.3

*Mean ± S.D.

TABLE 7
THE MEAN DURATION OF CONSTITUTIONAL SYMPTOMS
RELATED TO A FEELING OF WELL-BEING REPORTED
BY MEN AFFLICTED WITH A COMMON COLD

Group	N	Duration of Symptoms (days)
Vitamin C	6	0.8 ± 0.8*
Placebo	14	2.4 ± 2.1
		p < 0.05

On subsequent exercises an examination of the Vitamin C status of men was carried out by examining the whole-blood ascorbate levels before and immediately after the exercise. Table 8 shows the incidence of altered ascorbate status on four Northern exercises. In all cases, a significant number of men demonstrated a decrease in whole-blood ascorbate, however the magnitude of this decrease (Table 9) was significant on only three of the exercises. Coincidentally, these three exercises were supplied with the RP4 ration while the fourth exercise (Serial 56) received IRP field rations. The IRP ration provides approximately 50-90 mg of Vitamin C per day, about 50% of which is in a single fruit-drink mix and 50% is distributed throughout other ration components.

TABLE 8
INCIDENCE OF ALTERED WHOLE-BLOOD ASCORBATE STATUS
OCCURRING ON NORTHERN EXERCISES

Serial	N	% of Individuals Demonstrating a Decrease in Ascorbate	% of Individuals below 0.50 mg% Ascorbate	
			Pre-Exercise	Post-Exercise
NV 49	86	70	4	8
NV 51	29	83	28	41
NV 55	24	46	21	12
NV 56	34	47	32	32

TABLE 9
MEAN WHOLE-BLOOD ASCORBATE STATUS BEFORE AND
AFTER PARTICIPATION ON NORTHERN EXERCISES

Serial	N	Pre-Exercise Level mg%	Post-Exercise Mean Change	
			mg%	%
NV 49	86	1.05 ± 0.04*	-0.19 ± 0.04	-18
NV 51	29	0.86 ± 0.07	-0.21 ± 0.04	-24
NV 55	24	0.91 ± 0.10	-0.13 ± 0.06	-14
NV 56	34	0.76 ± 0.05	-0.03 ± 0.06	- 4

*Mean ± S.E.M.

One further point with reference to Table 8 is the rather surprising number of men who demonstrated whole-blood ascorbate levels lower than 0.50 mg%. This value is generally taken to indicate the threshold of a possible sub-clinical scorbutic condition. Two of the four serials examined post-exercise demonstrated a definite shift towards this subclinical scorbutic state, one (Serial 56) remained unchanged and the other (Serial 55) demonstrated a shift in the opposite direction.

In view of the variation in diet and distribution of change in ascorbate status, it is not possible from these data to determine whether the reduction in ascorbate levels, observed post-exercise on three of the four serials, was a consequence of reduced dietary intake of Vitamin C or a reflection of a possible increased requirement for this vitamin under the activity and exposure conditions existing on Northern operations. Clearly, a determination of ascorbate excretion is required before any estimate of requirement under these conditions can be made.

This study is part of a continuing program to assess the nature and incidence of health problems pertinent to Canadian military Northern operations. With regards to Vitamin C and its influence on general body health the data to date suggest that a daily supplement of 1000 mg Vitamin C appears to reduce the overall incidence of colds in transit military populations. It must be appreciated however, that the nature of the military exercise itself represents a marked departure from the "normal" daily routine. Over the period of this study, the men are transported by air into an adverse environment and live in close association with that

environment. Their dietary regimen is altered dramatically with regards both to frequency of meals and nature of food eaten. In view of these factors the results reported here do not necessarily characterize the civilian population in general. Further, insufficient data exist to enable us to determine whether the observed beneficial effect of Vitamin C observed in this study, is prophylactic or therapeutic, although the analysis of colds by tent groups suggests that the effect may be prophylactic. In addition the study was restricted to an examination of the efficacy of a daily 1000 mg dose of Vitamin C, which may represent neither the optimal nor minimal daily supplement required. The whole-blood ascorbate levels of individuals receiving a Vitamin C supplement were increased well above normal (100-150%). In view of the demonstrated decrease in whole-blood ascorbate occurring in non-supplemented men, the optimal dose of Vitamin C may be in a range which is sufficient to prevent such a decrease. Further work is required to clarify this situation.

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13. ABSTRACT This report describes results of an ongoing Vitamin C survey designed to examine both the Vitamin C status of troops and the effects of a daily Vitamin C supplement on the incidence and severity of colds in troops undergoing operational training. Results indicate that a daily 1000 mg supplement of Vitamin C reduced significantly the incidence of colds as assessed on the basis of symptom complexes reported on health survey cards. While the overall incidence of colds was influenced significantly by Vitamin C, both on an individual and a ten group basis, the duration of local cold symptoms was not. In those individuals who contracted a cold, nasal and throat and chest symptoms were observed to persist for similar periods of time in both placebo and Vitamin C supplemented groups. The Vitamin C group, however, did show a significant reduction in the duration of the more constitutional symptoms related to a general feeling of "well-being". Significant reduction of whole blood ascorbate levels was observed post-exercise on three separate serials of Exercise New Viking. Further work is required to determine whether this reduction in ascorbate status reflects altered dietary intake or an increased requirement for Vitamin C under the activity and exposure conditions experienced on Northern operations.			

KEY WORDS

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 Exercise New Viking
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 Common cold
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